

Australian Fgenesh++ Service: Trial User Summaries

Parice Brandies (University of Sydney)
and
Julia Voelker (Southern Cross University)

17 September 2021

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5513122

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

1. Context	3
2. Marsupial Genome Annotation Trial Summary	3
2.1 Summary	3
2.2 Inputs	3
2.3 Outputs	5
2.4 General Run Times:	5
3. Plant Genome Annotation Summary	7
3.1 Summary	7
3.2 Data Transfer and VM Access	7
3.3 Genome Annotation	7
3.4 Results	12
3.5 Ease of use	13

1. Context

These summaries are outcomes of trial use of the Australian Fgenesh++ Service by early adopters.

More information about this Service is available at <https://www.biocommons.org.au/fgenesh>.

For questions about this document please contact communities@biocommons.org.au.

2. Marsupial Genome Annotation Trial Summary

Compiled by Parice Brandies, University of Sydney

2.1 Summary

- The FGENESH++ pipeline usually predicts on average ~40,000 proteins for marsupial genomes of which ~50% are supported by mRNA evidence and a further ~10% are supported by protein evidence. The remaining genes correspond to Ab Initio predictions in gene regions where neither protein nor mRNA evidence was aligned (and hence may not be reliable). General BLAST searches (e.g. against SwissProt) can be used to filter the total number of annotations down to a final high-confidence set of annotations.
- Annotation BUSCO scores are highly dependent on input mRNA quality and genome quality but usually, achieve ~75-85% completeness of proteins with most of the remaining being fragmented. Note: Reference guided transcriptome assembly (rather than de novo assembly) is recommended for best results.
- When only protein evidence is used (if mRNA evidence is not available), results are similar with ~50% of annotations having protein evidence and similar BUSCO scores.
- Manual inspection of annotations using alignments to other species shows high-quality results
- See also Parice A. Brandies, Simon Tang, Robert S. P. Johnson, Carolyn J. Hogg, Katherine Belov, The first Antechinus reference genome provides a resource for investigating the genetic basis of semelparity and age-related neuropathologies, Gigabyte, 1, 2020 <https://doi.org/10.46471/gigabyte.7>

2.2 Inputs

Note: It is up to the user which evidence they wish to supply for gene predictions. Refer to the Softberry website for more information on available inputs and how they are used:

http://www.softberry.com/berry.phtml?topic=fgenesh_plus_plus&group=help&subgroup=pipelines

Protein Evidence

- Non-redundant metazoan protein database from NCBI (updated 2020 – provided by Softberry). Already available on the machine for all users.
 - Note: Custom protein databases can also be used – see the Softberry website at the top of this page for more information. Not tested on Marsupials.

mRNA Evidence

- Custom transcriptome assembled using either a de novo (Trinity) or reference guided (Hisat2 + stringtie) approach. Refguided is recommended based on results from marsupials. Uploaded by the user.
 - Note: Strict filtering and formatting are required if using a custom transcriptome dataset. More information can be provided by the BioCommons upon request. Recommendations for using a RefSeq mRNA dataset are provided on the Softberry website at the top of this page - not tested on Marsupials

Optimised Gene-Finding Parameters

- Tasmanian devil gene-finding matrix (provided by Softberry). Already available on the machine for all users.
 - Note: Other gene finding matrices may be made available upon request when working with a new type of organism. Please refer to the following link for a list of all available matrices:
http://www.softberry.com/berry.phtml?topic=org_list&group=programs&subgroup=gfind

General Pipeline Parameters

- Mammalian parameters (provided by Softberry). Already available on the machine for all users.
- Note: A set of non-mammal general parameters are also available for other non-mammalian species Already available on the machine for all users.

Genome Assembly

- Suggests having both the standard assembly and a corresponding repeat-masked genome, any level of genome quality is accepted though assembly quality is usually correlated with annotation quality. Uploaded by the user.
- Genome fasta files will be broken up into single fasta files to be run in parallel. Output can then be concatenated upon completion. Refer to BioCommons Tutorial (under development).

2.3 Outputs

Default

GenePred based Fgenesh++ annotation file for each scaffold

Optional

- Combined GenePred based FGENESH++ annotation file for the entire genome
- GFF3 or GenePred output
- mRNA multi-fasta file of predictions
- CDS multi-fasta file of predictions
- Protein multi-fasta file of predictions
- Refer to BioCommons Tutorial (under development) for how to make these additional outputs

2.4 General Run Times:

- Number of Marsupial species tested: 3
- Approximate genome size: ~3.3GB
- Pipeline set-up time (excluding custom mRNA formatting): <1 hour
- Wall time: ~2 days (independent of genome quality i.e. number of scaffolds/contigs)
- Optional output conversion: ~30 minutes

Comparison to MAKER annotation

- MAKER (1 round – no prior training):
- Number of proteins: 37,130
- BUSCO v3: C:65.9%[S:62.3%,D:3.6%],F:22.9%,M:11.2%,n:4104
- MAKER (3 rounds – training with SNAP + Augustus):
- Number of proteins: 28,703
- BUSCO v3: C:65.9%[S:62.4%,D:3.5%],F:24.6%,M:9.5%,n:4104
- FGENESH ++:
- Number of proteins: 42,454
- BUSCO v3: C:69.4%[S:66.3%,D:3.1%],F:25.9%,M:4.7%,n:4104
- Note: The above results were based on a draft genome assembly using only 10x data and a transcriptome that was assembled de novo.

2.5 To test program performance on your species of interest

- Fgenesh++ - Gene Finding with similarity-based on protein evidence and optimized gene-finding parameters from a closely related species
- http://www.softberry.com/berry.phtml?topic=fgenes_plus&group=programs&subgroup=gfs
- Fgenesh – Ab Initio predictions based on optimized gene-finding parameters from a closely related species
- <http://www.softberry.com/berry.phtml?topic=fgenesh&group=programs&subgroup=gfind>
- Note: The FGENESH++ command-line program is based on the above two programs but also incorporates mRNA-based evidence and at a much larger scale.

3. Plant Genome Annotation Summary

Compiled by Julia Voelker, Southern Cross University

3.1 Summary

- Apart from this ReadsMap issue, Fgenesh++ documentation was good to follow. Furthermore, Softberry has friendly and helpful customer support. Upon having problems with the protein database, they were quick to offer an inspection of the files and to run their own tests.
- Overall, taking the preparation of input files into account, Fgenesh++ took less time to run than GeneMark. GeneMark documentation took more time to understand because of the different modes (gmET+, gmEP+, gmES, ...) that can be run and the various input files that need to be created in advance when using the PLUS mode.
- Both tools have their advantages and disadvantages, and the prediction results might vary depending on the input genome.
- See also Julia Voelker, Mervyn Shepherd, Ramil Mauleon, A high-quality draft genome for *Melaleuca alternifolia* (tea tree): a new platform for evolutionary genomics of myrtaceous terpene-rich species, Gigabyte, 1, 2021
<https://doi.org/10.46471/gigabyte.28>

3.2 Data Transfer and VM Access

- Data transfer: scp using a private key
- VM Access: ssh using a private key

3.3 Genome Annotation

Genome Specifications

- Assembly type: MaSuRCA hybrid assembly using PacBio long reads and Illumina paired-end short reads
- Genome Assembly Size: 365 Mb
- No. Scaffolds: 3,217
- Scaffold N50: 1.8 Mb
- Complete BUSCOs Genome (Eudicot_odb10 in BUSCO v4.1.2): 98.1%

Other Data

- NCBI Plant NR protein database (provided by Softberry)
- Odb10-Viridiplantae protein database (downloaded from OrthoDB)

- closely related tree gene matrix (purchased by ABC from Softberry)
- RNAseq data from the same species but other individuals (downloaded from NCBI sequence read archive)

Run Information

- Fgenesh++ performance was compared to the [GeneMark prediction tool](#), which is free for academic institutions. Since Softberry provided the nr-plant protein DB, predictions were also run with a DB that's available on the internet ([odb10-plants](#)). The following runs were compared:

	NCBI nr-plant DB	odb10-plant DB	RNAseq alignments	Masked genome
Fgenesh++	X			X X
Fgenesh++	X			
Fgenesh++	X		X	
Fgenesh++		X	X	
GeneMarkES				
GeneMarkEP+		X		
GeneMarkET+		X	X	
GeneMarkET+	X		X	

- Specifications for Fgenesh++
 - Following Parice Brandies' guidelines (see Section 2), the genome was split into single fasta files. The separated scaffolds were then allocated to 63 lists so that each list contained approximately the same total sequence lengths
 - 64 CPUs, 256GB RAM
 - Total wall time using 63 cores = 12-15 hours per run
- Specifications for GeneMark:
 - 16 CPUs, 324GB RAM, Linux Red Hat V6
 - GeneMark-ES Suite version 4.59_lic, including GeneMark.hmm, GeneMark-ES, GeneMark-ET and GeneMark-EP algorithms
 - Total walltime for GeneMarkES= 2-4 hours
 - Total walltime for GeneMarkET+ and EP+ = 28-30 hours per run using 15 cores

Information regarding the odb10-plant DB

- The Fgenesh++ manual states that any fasta-formatted protein database should work, as long as it's indexed correctly

- The odb10-plant DB was downloaded and indexed but caused a prot-map error in Fgenesh++
- Upon contacting Softberry and investigating the DB file, it was discovered that some protein sequences were too short. The fasta file was then filtered for sequences that are at least as long as the shortest sequences of the nr-plant DB (6 amino acids).
- Fgenesh++ ran without errors with the modified (> 5 AA) odb10-plant DB

Storage Requirements

- Input files = 354MB total (small plant genome)
- Final output = <500MB in total

Assessment of predictions

- BUSCO scores for the predicted proteomes
- InterProScan was used to identify conserved PfamA domains in the predicted protein sequences. The results were filtered for domains known in eudicots, and based on the total no. of predicted proteins, the percentage of proteins with hits to a eudicot Pfam domain was calculated.
- The identified PfamA domains were filtered for Terpene Synthase domains. Based on other related genomes, the number was expected to be 80-130.
- The total number of predicted protein-coding genes was expected to be around 30,000-45,000, based on annotations of related plants

	Busco v 4.1.2, run with Galaxy Australia (https://usegalaxy.org.au/), dataset used: eudicots_odb10, mode: proteome					
Predictions	BUSCO score	Complete BUSCOs	Complete and single-copy	Complete and duplicated	Fragmented	Missing
Fgenesh masked	84.4%	1,964	1,834	130	165	197
Fgenesh	90.5%	2,104	1,958	146	125	97
Fgenesh +RNAseq	91.7%	2,133	1,986	147	120	73
Fgenesh odb10 +RNAseq	92.8%	2,157	2,016	141	93	76
gmES	63.2%	1,471	1,366	105	402	453
gmEP+	96.0%	2,234	2,080	154	52	40
gmET+	96.4%	2,243	2,087	156	45	38
gmET+ nr-plant	96.6%	2,247	2,092	155	44	35

	Screen for known PfamA protein domains			Screen for TPS motifs
Predictions	total no. of predicted protein-coding genes	no. of proteins with a hit to Eudicot Pfam domains	Percentage with eudicot hits	genes encoding PfamA TPS domains
Fgenesh masked	27,099	17,787	65.64	25
Fgenesh	50,883	30,939	60.80	97
Fgenesh +RNAseq	52,748	31,380	59.49	96
Fgenesh odb10 +RNAseq	52,436	31,125	59.36	101
gmES	102,542	33,888	33.05	103
gmEP+	81,308	31,761	39.06	100

gmET+	82,580	31,700	38.39	100
gmET+ nr-plant	82,737	31,782	38.41	100

Fgenes++ was run with nr-plant protein DB, unless noted otherwise.

gm (GeneMark) ET+ and EP+ were run with odb10-plant DB, unless noted otherwise.

gmES = no hints; gmET+ =protein evidence + RNAseq alignments; gmEP+ = protein evidence

TPS= Terpene Synthase; odb10 = odb10-Viridiplantae protein DB; nr-plant = NCBI nr-plant protein DB

3.4 Results

Fgenesh++ predictions

- Low complexity and simple repeats were not masked for the masked genome prediction. Still, the number of predicted protein-coding genes was considerably lower than the predicted genes in the unmasked genome. Furthermore, the no. of hits to Pfam domains and the no. of predicted proteins with high similarity to TPS domains was lower than expected.
- The high repetitive content of the genome might have led to the masking of gene-coding sequences. Especially for TPS, it is known that they evolve through tandem duplication. Thus it was decided to run all following predictions on the unmasked genome, and mask repeats further downstream.
- Since no transcriptome for the sequenced individual was available, paired RNAseq reads from other individuals of the same species were aligned to the assembly. The Fgenesh++ predictions improved with the provided RNAseq evidence. BUSCO scores, as well as PfamA domain counts, increased slightly.
- Upon using another database (odb10-plants), the BUSCO scores increased. However, this assessment might be biased, since the odb10-eudicot DB used in BUSCO shares sequences with the odb10-plant DB. The number of sequences with homology to PfamA domains was lower than for the nr-plant prediction. However, results are still comparable and show that Fgenesh++ also works when other protein databases than the NCBI nr-DB are provided as evidence.

GeneMark predictions

- GeneMark generally predicted a higher number of protein-coding genes than Fgenesh++, which indicates that Fgenesh++ might have more stringent prediction parameters or applies improved filtering after ab initio predictions. Furthermore, Fgenesh++ used a species-specific matrix, while GeneMark can only use provided RNA and protein evidence.
- Even though Fgenesh++ BUSCO scores outperformed the gmES ab initio prediction, the number of proteins with hits to Pfam domains were still comparable. The majority of gmES predicted proteins, however, returned no hits. The total no. of predicted genes highly exceeded the expected number, which indicates that extensive filtering of GeneMark predictions might be required, while Fgenesh++ is closer to expected values.
- When providing the same RNAseq read evidence as in Fgenesh++, the number of predicted proteins containing conserved Pfam domains was similar. Furthermore, the BUSCO score for GeneMark+RNA predictions exceeded Fgenesh++ scores. Interestingly, while Fgenesh++ had a better BUSCO score when run with the odb10-DB, the score for gmET+ predictions improved slightly with the nr-plant DB. The differences, however, between gmET+ odb10 and gmET+ nr-plant are marginal.

Fgenesh++ vs GeneMark

- The two protein databases (odb10-plant and nr-plant) worked well for both prediction tools and resulted in comparable numbers of protein-coding genes. For Fgenesh++, it has to be kept in mind that the database mustn't contain any too short sequences. Fgenesh++ ab initio prediction will still run, but the protein alignment step will be omitted.
Overall, predicted gene numbers in Fgenesh++ are closer to the expected values. In both tools, the addition of RNAseq alignment information improved the number of predictions and BUSCO scores, even though the transcriptome reads were not obtained from the same individual.
- Masking of the genome pre-prediction did not work well for this plant genome. This might be explained by the high repeat content in the genome. Related plant genomes are reported to have remarkably high tandem duplication levels.
- Thus, both prediction tools were run on the unmasked genome, and some intensive post-prediction filtering will be required, especially for GeneMark output.

3.5 Ease of use

Protein database input

- For Fgenesh++ runs, the protein databases only need to be indexed and alignments to the assembly are part of the pipeline. Furthermore, the output annotation file lists the protein evidence as part of the predicted gene name.
- For GeneMark, the protein database can be provided when doing a prediction in GeneMarkEP mode. The protein splice alignment will then be created as part of the run.
- If GeneMark is to be run in PLUS mode, however (gmEP+ or gmET+), it not only uses protein alignments as evidence but also another subset of high confidence protein evidence created from the same protein database. This evidence file needs to be created with ProtHint, which is included in the GeneMark package but has to be run separately. ProtHint requires the protein database as input and will either create a GeneMarkES prediction as part of the pipeline, or this step can be skipped when providing a GeneMarkES gtf file. ProtHint will then run protein splice alignments and create two sets of protein hints, one containing all reported hints, and the other one only listing high confidence evidence. ProtHint took 7-10 hours to run on this plant genome on 15 cores.

RNAseq read alignments

- RNAseq read splice alignments need to be provided to GeneMarkET as intron coordinates files in GFF format. The GeneMark package already contains a script that can convert STAR alignment output into the required GFF file.
- For Fgenesh++, RNAseq read alignments can be provided to improve gene models. The only information provided in the manual is that *.sites files

containing potential splice sites must be produced prior to running the prediction. It took some searching to find out that .sites alignment files can only be created with Softberry's ReadsMap tool, which can be downloaded for free. Furthermore, the user has to keep in mind that Fgenesh++ will look for .sites files for every single scaffold, so ReadsMap should not be run on the whole assembly, but on separated scaffolds/contigs instead. Also, the name of the file needs to be the same as the scaffold.fasta file (just with the .sites ending), or Fgenesh will report an error.